

Financing Sustainable Research Software

B.Beygu Koopmans¹, Rolf W. Hut², O.R. Williams³

^{1&3} Center for Information Technology, Smitsborg, Nettelbosje 1, 9747 AJ, Groningen, The Netherlands

² Department of Water Management, Delft University of Technology, Delft, The Netherlands

Abstract

This study investigates the practices, challenges, and funding mechanisms related to the maintenance and sustainability of research software in the Natural and Engineering Sciences (NES) domain in the Netherlands. Through a national survey targeting researchers and professionals, we analyzed the roles, institutional contexts, and funding structures that support research software. The results show that research software is developed and used across many research fields, often by individuals holding multiple roles—such as *developer*, *maintainer*, and *researcher*. However, software maintenance remains under-recognized, and is rarely embedded in formal responsibilities, institutional planning or funding mechanisms. Budgeting for long-term maintenance is often absent at both project and organizational levels, and recognition in career progression is inconsistent. Field-specific analysis revealed strong disciplinary contrasts: in Astronomy & Astrophysics, maintenance responsibilities are more often formalized and backed by allocated time, while in Computer Science and Engineering, maintenance remains largely informal despite ongoing effort—highlighting how undervaluation persists even in highly technical domains. Our findings suggest that sustainable research software development requires institutional recognition, transparent funding practices, and explicit allocation of time and responsibility in both job roles and employment contracts.

Keywords: Research software, TDCC-NES, Research software maintenance, Natural and Engineering Sciences

1. Introduction

Developing research software is a fundamental aspect of research in the NES domain. Such software ranges from tools developed during PhD projects, to infrastructure services that support novel data processing pipelines, to software used in experimental setups for instrument control and data collection. These tools often play a critical role in advancing scientific discovery and can have long-term impact well beyond the lifespan of the original project. Despite their importance, however, research software frequently faces sustainability challenges, especially once project funding ends. Sustaining research software requires continuous human effort and dedicated financial resources.

Due to time-limited funding and a focus on short-term research outputs, the maintenance and long-term usability of research software are rarely accounted for in research budgets. As a result, researchers often absorb these so-called "hidden costs" themselves to keep essential tools functional. These challenges are increasingly recognized in national research infrastructure strategies and highlight a significant gap in current funding policies. Without appropriate planning

and investment, valuable software risks becoming unusable, which in turn threatens the reproducibility and continuity of scientific research.

This project is set out to investigate the financial aspects of sustaining research software in the NES domain. Specifically, it aimed to identify the full range of costs, including hidden and long-term maintenance costs—and to assess the benefits and risks associated with continued software support. Through a national survey engaging researchers and academic professionals, the project sought to uncover structural *bottlenecks* in how funding is distributed and sustained. These issues are explicitly acknowledged in the Thematic Digital Competence Center (TDCC) NES roadmap, where long-term software maintenance was classified as an “unknown cost” and identified as one of the “bottleneck” challenges.

This paper is organized as follows. [Section 1](#) provides the background and goals of the project and outlines the types of research software considered. [Section 2](#) describes the data collection process, including how the national survey was designed, distributed, and structured. [Section 3](#) details the data cleaning and analysis methodology, focusing on how responses were standardized and interpreted. [Section 4](#) presents the key findings, based on a comprehensive analysis of the survey data and the relationships between research roles, software use, and funding mechanisms. Finally, [Section 5](#) concludes with a summary of results and their implications for funding policy and research infrastructure planning. [Appendix 1](#) shows free text answers or answers categorized as *Other*. [Appendix 2](#) gives the full list of survey questions and [Appendix 3](#) includes a summary of the survey branching logic.

1.1 Project Goal

The goal of this project is to Investigate and discover:

- Financial awareness of the long-term maintenance and sustainability of research software, depending on the characteristics of that software (scope, community, quality, novelty).
- Bottlenecks in the distribution of financial resources within national research institutions.
- The challenges which are faced with maintaining and disseminating software.
- Who *develops* and *maintains* research software?
- Cost benefit and risk analysis focused on human resources,

We focus on the NES research population in the Dutch Universities and the [NWO-I](#) institutes as defined in the [TDCC-NES roadmap](#).

1.2 Types of Research Software Taken into Consideration in the Project

Creating a definition of research software is outside of the scope of this project. Therefore, the definition created by the FAIR for Research Software Working Group (a joint initiative of RDA, ReSA and FORCE11¹) is adopted for the scope of this project. This definition is also utilized by the eScience Center’s Practical Guide to Research Software Management Plans² and the NWO.

Category 1

This software is typically developed for a *specific analysis* (e.g. drawing a graph) or *one-off project* (e.g. practical examples in a course). The developer is the primary user, and it is not intended to be used beyond a defined period or in a different context.

As this software is not intended to be used by others, either directly or as a dependency, its influence beyond the scope for which it was intended is small. While measures to enable its *reuse* (documentation, versioning, archiving) are appropriate, no additional maintenance planning is required.

Examples:

- A script that is used to create and format a single figure for a publication, for example, when using a plotting package such as *ggplot2 (R)* or *Matplotlib (Python)*.
- Software written as part of a project to automate an administrative or routine process, e.g. monitoring a process or generating document templates.
- Software written specifically for the analysis of a single experiment, data processing, and presentation of its results.

Category 2

Software of this level is typically developed as a *research project* or is the primary output of a research project. Although usually developed for a single purpose, it incorporates functionality that may be of *use to others*, either as a standalone *tool, library, or module* in an existing tool.

Software developed (e.g. as a part of a PhD project) where the end goal is to contribute to an already existing scientific software, potentially used significantly by researchers from the same field to analyze, process or simulate data.

This software may have a direct influence on other researchers (e.g. project(s), research group(s) and/or software(s) even if this was not the primary intention when it was conceptualized. It may implement a new or higher performance algorithm and can be applied to different input data. It could be simulation software that implements one or more models and/or numerical methods, e.g., computational fluid dynamics, chemical interactions, planetary evolution, partial differential equation solvers, numerical integration, etc. This type of research software is more complicated and/or larger, in terms of lines of code, than those in Category 1.

Examples:

- [AOFlagger](#) : Tool to detect background radio signals which do not originate from an astronomical object. Developed as part of a PhD project and still being used by the community as being the best flagger so far.
- "[Clair](#)" stands for "C/C++ language analysis in Rascal". Developed by a PhD candidate at TU Eindhoven who wrote this bridge (a Java/Rascal library) between an open C++ compiler and the Rascal syntax tree analysis and transformation features. The goal was to extract software models (communicating state machines) from legacy C++ code using Clair. Applied later for fundamental research on the history and evolution of UNIX source code and in applied research for C++ code refactoring, and software architectural rule violations at Philips Healthcare (for example).
- [Ppfx](#): Tool for spectral analysis and model fitting. Developed almost 20 years ago and still being used by the community so far with 1708 citations.
- [Rascal](#): Programming language that accurately analyzes, transforms, generates, and visualizes source code in any programming language. Used for empirical research in software engineering, prototyping new tools for programmers and generating code and analyses from formal models.
- Earth science models such as
 - [PCRGlobWB](#) (hydrological model developed by Utrecht University).
- Tooling to process (earth system) data or to run (earth system) models.
 - [eWatercycle](#), platform to run hydrological models FAIR, built by TU Delft and NLeSC, hopefully maintained in future by community.

- ESMValTool, suite of analyses tools to make analyses of climate data produced by different research groups in a consistent manner. Developed and maintained by community. <https://github.com/ESMValGroup/ESMValTool>

Category 3

Research software of this level was designed, or has evolved, to be *mission critical*, reliability is of utmost importance. All possible actions should be taken to ensure reliability, which include software architecture design, code standards, the use of comprehensive cross-platform automated unit and functional testing frameworks, dependency management, and code auditing. In addition, legal development requirements, such as traceability, right to use, right to inspect, right to distribute, etc., and process documentation.

Software developed to be used as *part of experiments*, to *control instruments* and *robots*, or to *collect data in the laboratories*. Such software is not only critical in acquiring the data to analyze but also in reproducibility of the experiments.

Examples:

- [IRAF: Image Reduction and Analysis Facility](#): Data reduction package of astronomical images and spectra in pixel array form.
- [Maracas](#): Measures theoretical introduction of API breaking changes in library projects, and actual breakage in their client projects on ecosystem scale (such as all open-source Java projects in the world).
- [ECMWF Integrated Forecasting System \(IFS\)](#): starting point of way too much documentation.

2. Data Collection

The data was collected through a structured online survey designed in *Qualtrics* and distributed among researchers and professionals involved in research software within the Natural and Engineering Sciences (NES) domain of the Dutch research institutions as defined in the [TDCC-NES roadmap](#). The survey remained open for responses between May 1st, 2024, and August 31st, 2024. A total of 197 responses were received. The survey was evaluated in advance, and the questions were reviewed by colleagues outside the project team to ensure clarity and relevance.

Recruitment was conducted through multiple channels, including local Digital Competence Centers (DCCs), the TDCC-NES community, and personal professional networks. An anonymous survey link was distributed via email across these networks to reach a broad and relevant audience. All the Dutch Universities and NOW I institutions were reached out.

2.1 Survey Structure

The survey consisted of 27 substantive questions in a variety of formats, including *multiple-choice* (with some allowing multiple selections), *free-text* responses, *rating scales*, and *percentage-based distributions* (see [Appendix 2](#) for the full list of questions). Participants could choose more than one option where applicable and were also able to provide their own answers in *free-text* form. If none of the listed options fit their situation, they could use the *Other* option to write a custom response.

Conditional branching logic was used to tailor the questionnaire based on respondents' answers (e.g., only those involved in funded projects were shown financial-related questions), ensuring relevance and reducing survey fatigue (see [Appendix 3](#) for conditional branching logic of the survey questions). As a result, not all participants will answer every question. Certain questions are only seen by participants based on previous responses. Funding-related questions are only

shown to those working on funded projects. The survey may end early for some participants based on their responses.

For example, participants who indicated no involvement in research software were automatically redirected to the end of the survey. As a result, not all 197 participants answered all 27 questions. Each response was anonymized, with a unique *RecordID* assigned to allow consistent linking across questions for each participant.

No personal data—such as names, addresses, email addresses, or the names of participants' organizations—was collected. At the beginning of the survey, participants were asked to give *informed consent* before proceeding.

3. Data Analysis

A comprehensive cleaning and restructuring process was applied to the raw survey data to enable thematic interpretation, support conditional logic, and allow for cross-question analysis.

3.1 General Approach

Each survey question was exported from *Qualtrics* as a separate CSV file. These files were cleaned individually, then merged into a unified dataset using the unique *ResponseID* assigned to each participant. The cleaning pipeline included:

- Renaming and standardizing column headers for clarity and consistency.
- Normalizing *multi-option* responses (e.g., comma-separated selections) into structured formats.
- Trimming and capitalizing *free-text* entries to reduce variability.
- Handling missing values with care—preserving them when they reflect non-responses due to survey branching logic.
- Standardizing terminology across responses and applying custom groupings to harmonize key variables (e.g., institutional types, research fields, roles, and job titles).

After this preparation, both descriptive and exploratory analyses were conducted to uncover patterns and relationships within and across responses. Using *ResponseID*, answers were matched across questions to enable compound analysis, e.g., comparing software roles with *time allocations*, or *institutional type* with awareness of *maintenance funding*.

3.2 Standardization and Grouping

While most questions followed a similar cleaning procedure, some required additional harmonization. Where appropriate, thematic groupings were applied to consolidate the large variation in *free-text* responses or multiple-choice combinations:

- *Institutional affiliations* (**Question 1**) were grouped into eight standard categories to allow comparison between universities, research institutes, industry, and hybrid affiliations.
- *Research fields* (**Question 2**) were mapped to ten overarching NES research domains using a custom keyword-based classifier.
- *Roles and job titles* (**Question 3**, **Question 18**) were unified into broader categories to support analysis of maintenance responsibilities and career stages.
- *Project and grant names* (**Question 10**) were manually reviewed and categorized where possible.
- *Percentage-based answers* (**Question 5**, **Question 20**) were cleaned to ensure total value remained interpretable and logically consistent.

- *Ranking and importance scores (Question 21)* were grouped by theme to analyze challenge categories.

These steps ensured interpretability across heterogeneous answer types and improved the quality of subsequent visualizations and summaries.

3.3 Analysis of Free-text Responses

For open-ended *Other* answers or comment fields, responses were first standardized (e.g., *capitalization, spacing*), then grouped manually or using *keyword matching* when common themes emerged. These responses were either:

- Integrated into primary categories when clearly aligned, or
- Reported separately in [Appendix 1](#) when they reflected uncategorizable answers.

3.4 Linking Questions and Enabling Cross-Analysis

Because of the survey's branching logic, not all participants answered every question. Conditional display rules were respected during analysis. For instance, funding-related questions (**Question 11–Question 16**) were only shown to respondents working on funded projects.

Cross-question comparisons were enabled using the *ResponseID* field, allowing us to analyze:

- Whether institutional type correlated with funding structures (**Question 1 × Question 11–Question 13**),
- How roles and career stages influenced software responsibilities (**Question 3 × Question 18**),
- How recognition patterns varied across disciplines (**Question 2 × Question 22–Question 25**).

4. Results

Based on the intent and the context, survey questions can be grouped into the following categories shown in **Table 1**. In the following subsections results of categories are given.

Table 1. Thematic grouping of survey questions by topic and question numbers.

Question Type	Questions
Participant profiles & roles	Q1-Q5, Q8
Context & use of the research software	Q6-Q7
Project & funding awareness	Q9-Q10
Budget allocation & financial sustainability	Q11-Q16
Human resources & maintenance responsibilities	Q17-Q20
Recognition	Q21-Q26

4.1 Participant Profiles and Roles

Participant affiliations

The survey received responses from a broad range of individuals involved in research software activities in the Dutch NES domain. A total of 165 participants answered this question where respondents were allowed to select multiple answers. As shown in **Figure 1**, 60% of the participants reported working at a university. This was followed by respondents affiliated with NWO-I institutes (14.5%) and organizations such as the eScience Center, DANS, or SURF (12.7%).

Several participants indicated dual affiliations, including combinations like University & NWO-I Institute (3.6%), University & Small Enterprise (1 respondent) or University & TO2 Organization (1 respondent). Less frequent affiliations included Government institutions, Applied Universities, and Large Enterprises — each selected by around 1.8% of respondents.

Non-traditional affiliations given as *Other* option, included “Open Source project with own governance”, “Self-employed research software engineer”, and “UMC” (see **Table 3** in [Appendix 1](#)).

Q1: What type of institute do you work in?

Figure 1. Participant affiliations by institutional type (multiple answers allowed).

Research fields

Regarding disciplinary background, participants represented a wide range of research fields (**Figure 2**). Since the respondents are asked to provide a written answer to this question, we grouped by the answer and created categories to simplify displaying the results ([Appendix 1, Table 4](#)). The largest group identified with Astronomy & Astrophysics (22% of 153 respondents), followed by Earth & Environmental Sciences (~10%), and Life Sciences & Medicine (~10%). Other well-represented fields included Mathematics & Computational Science, Computer Science & AI, and Physics & Applied Physics.

20 responses could not be cleanly mapped to predefined domains and were grouped under *Other*, including fields such as *cryptology*, *hydrometeorology*, or roles in *technical research support*.

Q2: What is your research field??

Figure 2. Distribution of research fields among respondents, grouped by disciplinary category.

Job titles

Job titles within institutions were highly diverse (**Figure 3**). Of the 154 responses, the two most common answers were Research Software Engineer (20%) and *Other* (21%). However, the majority, 54% of titles belong to the combination of *senior and junior researchers* — Professor, Assistant and Associate professor, PhD, Postdoctoral fellow, MSc student —.

As given in [Appendix 1, Table 5](#), the *free-text* job titles under the option *Other* included a wide array of professional functions. Examples include “Instrument Scientist”, “Programme Manager”, “Department Head”, “Group Leader”, “Senior Research Software Engineer”, “Data Steward”, “Lecturer”, “Product Owner”, and “Head of Technical Operations”, among many others. Some titles pointed to hybrid or interdisciplinary responsibilities such as “Research Software & Strategist”, “Senior Scientist”, and “Technology Lead (associate professor equivalent)”.

This range of responses highlights that the people contributing to research software development and maintenance are not confined to a single job category or discipline. Instead, they span academic, technical, managerial, and operational domains, reflecting the complex and evolving nature of research software work across institutions.

Figure 3. Job titles of participants, showing frequency and diversity of formal roles.

Activities concerning research software

When asked about their activities concerning research software, most participants reported engagement in multiple roles (**Figure 4**). Respondents were allowed to select multiple answers among the predefined ones that describe their activities the best. If they do not engage in any activities concerning research software, they could select the answer *None*. In this case, participants were not able to continue with the rest of the survey. And, if they are involved activities other than the given options, they could explain them in the *Other* option ([Appendix 1, Table 6](#)).

The most common combination was Develop, Maintain, Facilitate/Manage, Use, Other (35 respondents, 22%), reflecting the many responsibilities many holds. Other frequent combinations included subsets of these roles—Develop & Maintain, Use only, or Develop & Use—demonstrating that respondents often contribute across development and user-oriented activities.

The majority selected more than one activity, indicating that many individuals take on overlapping responsibilities such as developing, maintaining, and facilitating research software. This reinforces the idea that research software roles are multifaceted and often not confined to a single task.

In addition to the predefined activities—Develop, Maintain, Facilitate/Manage, Use, and None—a small number of participants (n=6) provided *free-text* responses under *Other*. These included activities such as “Algorithm development”, “Teaching”, “Contributing to open-source projects”, or “Managing HPC infrastructure”. Some of these activities fall under the categories of Develop, Facilitate and Use, while others — Teaching, acquire, set up, manage, and maintain HPC infrastructure — fall outside the specific scope of this survey.

Q4: Which of the following activities concerning research software do you spend your work time on?

Figure 4. Activities related to research software development and use (multiple selections possible).

Work time spent on different activities related to research software

In **Question 5**, participants were asked to estimate what percentage of their work time they spend on different activities related to research software. As shown in **Figure 5**, the results reveal that the largest share of time is allocated to two activities: Developing research software, with an average of 31.8%, and Using research software in one's own research, close behind 31.1%.

These results confirm earlier findings from **Question 4**, where most respondents identified themselves as both developers and users of research software.

Q5: Average Percentage of Work Time by Activity

Figure 5. Average percentage of time spent on different research software activities.

The next most time-consuming activity was Facilitating or managing others, averaging 27.5%. This suggests that many participants are not only engaged in hands-on work but also play coordination, mentorship, or leadership roles in software efforts.

In contrast, maintaining research software had the lowest average time allocation at 16.9%, supporting a pattern observed elsewhere in the survey: although maintenance is critical to sustainability, it often receives less focus in practice.

Most of the *free-text* responses in the *Other* category elaborate on or complement the predefined roles (**Table 6**). For instance, participants mentioned responsibilities like “algorithm development”, “contributing to open source”, or “managing infrastructure”, which align closely with the broader activities of development or facilitation. These additions further emphasize the range of work covered under existing categories rather than introducing entirely distinct roles.

Overall, the **Question 5** responses emphasize the multi-faceted nature of research software work, with participants distributing their time across technical, research and managerial or coordination tasks, while also highlighting a potential vulnerability around ongoing maintenance.

Roles concerning research software

Participants were also asked to describe their specific role in relation to the research software they work with. 134 answered **Question 8** where they were allowed to select more than one role that describes them the most (see **Figure 6**). Researcher Developing Software and Researcher Using Software, were the most common roles each selected by 74 participants, indicating that many researchers are both creators and users of the tools they develop. Additionally, 59 participants identified as Principal Investigators (PIs) or Managers involved in creating software, and others noted roles such as Maintaining Software—either as a researcher (n=35) or as a PI/Manager (n=33). Notably, 27 participants (17%) stated they were not researchers but still write software, emphasizing the contribution of dedicated technical staff or support roles to the research software landscape. A smaller number (n=12) selected the option *Other*.

Figure 6. Roles related to research software reported by participants (multiple roles selectable).

Similar to **Question 4**, many participants selected multiple roles in **Question 8**. This highlights the reality that individuals often wear several hats—such as being both developers and maintainers—which aligns with how research software is developed and sustained across institutions. Participants who identify as *developers*, also report spending work time on *development* in **Question 4**.

While 12 participants selected the option *Other*, a closer inspection reveals that most of these responses mirror or extend the predefined categories (**Appendix 1, Table 7**), aligning closely with roles such as Developing, Maintaining, or Using software. Others described facilitation or consultancy work, which conceptually overlaps with the role of PI/Manager Creating or Maintaining Software, or with technical support staff.

Activities by research field

In **Figure 7**, we present a heatmap displaying the cross-correlation with research fields on the y-axis and research software related activities on the x-axis. The color intensity reflects the number of participants selecting each combination. As shown, participants across nearly all research domains reported engagement in software development. This was especially prominent in Astronomy & Astrophysics, where 30 respondents indicated involvement in software development — the highest single-field count.

Figure 7. Heatmap of research software activities by research field (Question 2 vs Question 4).

The *Other* category also showed strong engagement across all activity types, likely reflecting interdisciplinary or uncategorized roles. Fields such as Physics & Applied Physics, Mathematics & Computational Science, and Earth & Environmental Sciences also had notable developer representation.

The activity of Facilitating or Managing research software was again most prominent in Astronomy & Astrophysics (23 respondents), followed by Life Sciences & Medicine and Earth & Environmental Sciences. This suggests these fields may have stronger support structures or more formal coordination roles embedded in their research software workflows.

Engagement in *software maintenance* was more modest overall but remained visible, especially in Astronomy & Astrophysics (25 mentions) and in the *Other* category (11 mentions). This aligns with earlier findings showing that maintenance is widespread but often undervalued or informally assigned.

Using research software was common across all domains, with high counts in Astronomy & Astrophysics, Life Sciences & Medicine, and the *Other* category, confirming the essential role of software in modern research workflows.

Some fields such as Linguistics & Cognitive Science and Engineering & Technology showed relatively fewer responses across most activities, but this may reflect smaller sample sizes from those disciplines rather than lower engagement.

Roles by research field

As shown in **Figure 8**, the most common role across all research fields is Researcher – Developer. This suggests that many researchers are not only users of software but also directly involved in its creation as part of their research process. This is most prominent in Astronomy & Astrophysics

The second most common role is Non-Researcher – Developer, which is notably frequent in Computer Science & AI, Astronomy & Astrophysics, and Earth & Environmental Sciences. This contributes to the essential contribution of scientific programmers, research software engineers and technical staff, particularly in disciplines where software systems are large-scale or infrastructure intensive.

Figure 8. Roles concerning research software, broken down by research field (Question 2 vs Question 8).

The role of Researcher – Maintainer is comparatively **underrepresented** across most research fields. Unlike Developer or User roles, maintenance is *rarely self-identified* as a core responsibility — even in fields with high software usage or production.

While **Astronomy & Astrophysics** has the highest number of total participants, its role distribution is notably concentrated. Respondents from this field most commonly identify as Researcher – Developer, PI – Creator, or Non-Researcher – Developer. Roles such as Researcher – Maintainer or Researcher – User are *rarely selected*.

However, this pattern stands in contrast to the findings from **Figure 7 (Question 2 vs Question 4)**, which shows that Astronomy & Astrophysics participants report the highest involvement in maintenance activities. This discrepancy suggests that although researchers in this field are actively maintaining software, they may *not formally recognize or label themselves* as maintainers.

Smaller fields like Linguistics & Cognitive Science or Interdisciplinary & Cross-Domain report fewer responses overall but still show engagement in core roles such as Developer or User.

Time spent on activities per role

To assess whether participants' self-identified roles (**Question 4**) align with how they actually allocate their work time (**Question 5**), we compared average percentages of time spent on four core research software activities for each role group (see **Figure 9**).

Figure 9. Time spent on activities by role type (Question 4 vs Question 5 cross-tab).

As expected, respondents who selected *Develop* as one of their roles reported spending the highest proportion of their time on software development, averaging 31.8%. Similarly, those who selected *Use* reported the highest average time spent on software use (31.1%), confirming a strong alignment between reported roles and work activities.

However, a clear discrepancy appears for *maintenance*: even participants who explicitly selected *Maintain* as a role reported spending only 16.9% of their time on that activity — barely higher than other groups. This suggests that maintenance work may be systematically under-resourced or undervalued, even by those officially responsible for it.

Participants with *Facilitate/Manage* roles reported a more *balanced distribution* of time across development (26.5%), facilitation (27.5%), and usage (24.4%). This reflects the hybrid nature of these roles, which often involve coordination, mentoring, or overseeing development while still contributing technically.

Overall, the heatmap confirms a *strong correlation* between roles and activity types for development and use. However, it also highlights a *systemic gap* for software maintenance — an activity that is both essential and frequently underrepresented in role identity, time allocation, and funding structures

4.2 Context and Use of Research Software

In this section we delve more into the question of for what purpose research software is developed. Participants were asked about the intended audience and classification of the research software they work with. As shown in **Figure 10**, a large portion of respondents indicated that their software is not developed solely for personal use. Instead, most reported building tools either for a research group or community (n=69, 51%) or for both personal and group use (n=56, 41%). Only a small subset of respondents (n=9) reported working on software that is intended solely for personal use. These results suggest that while some software remains project-specific, the majority of tools are built with broader scientific use and reusability in mind.

Q6: Is the research software you work with developed for personal use or for a research group/community?

Figure 10. Intended audience for the research software developed or used by participants. Categories of research software

Previously, research software categories are described in [Section 1.2](#). These categories are based on the development goals and the intended target audience for which the software is created. As a follow-up to **Question 6**, participants were asked to indicate which category (or categories) the research software they work with falls into. They could select multiple options, and **Figure 11** shows the total count of selections per software type.

Q7: Which category does the research software you work on or with fall into?

Figure 11. Frequency of software types by category (multiple categories selectable).

The most frequently selected classification was Specific Methods (n=92), suggesting that many tools are designed for research-field-specific tasks, such as instrument control, data acquisition, or support specific experiments. This was followed closely by **Contribution to Community** (n=82) and **Core Infrastructure** (n=74). This distribution shows that research software in the NES domain often fulfills multiple roles—from supporting individual experiments to contributing to long-term infrastructure and scientific communities. Only two participants selected *Other* suggesting that the predefined categories captured the majority of use cases effectively.

Research software types by research field

To better understand how software classification varies across scientific disciplines, we examined the relationship between participants' research fields (**Question 2**) and the types of software they reported working on (**Question 7**). **Figure 12** presents a heatmap of this cross-correlation, with research fields on the y-axis and software categories on the x-axis. The color intensity reflects the number of participants selecting each combination.

Figure 12. Heatmap of software categories by research field (Question 2 vs Question 7).

We observed that Astronomy & Astrophysics contributed significantly across all software types—most notably in Specific Methods (n=24) and Community Contributions (n=21). This suggests that researchers in this field produce both specialized tools for domain-specific tasks and reusable software for broader community use.

Participants in Earth & Environmental Sciences also reported high involvement in both Community Contributions (n=11) and Core Infrastructure (n=13). This aligns with the collaborative and data-intensive nature of environmental science, where tools often support shared sensor platforms, geospatial datasets, and modeling environments.

Fields like Chemistry & Material Science, Life Sciences & Medicine, and Mathematics & Computational Science showed a more balanced distribution across software categories, indicating mixed contributions to both reusable and task-specific tools.

In contrast, fields such as Engineering & Technology, Linguistics & Cognitive Science, and Interdisciplinary or Cross-Domain research reported fewer total contributions and a narrower focus, often limited to Specific Methods. This may reflect the smaller number of participants from these fields or a greater focus on internal tools over community infrastructure.

Interestingly, participants who selected *Other* (see **Table 2**) as their research field also made substantial contributions to all three software types, particularly to Core Infrastructure (n=10) and Specific Methods (n=13). This highlights the importance of cross-disciplinary or less formally categorized contributors in the research software ecosystem.

In summary, we found that software type is closely linked to disciplinary context. Fields like Astronomy and Earth Sciences show stronger engagement with shared, reusable tools, while other domains focus more on targeted, domain-specific development.

4.3 Project and Funding Awareness

To understand how research software development aligns with structured projects and funding mechanisms, we asked participants whether the software they work with is developed as part of a specific project, and if so, how that project is funded. As shown in **Figure 13**, the majority of respondents (105 out of 134) reported that their software is developed within a project-based context, while 29 participants indicated that their software is not associated with any formal project. This underscores the widespread role of formal projects as vehicles for research software development across the NES research community.

Figure 13. Whether the research software is part of a formal project.

Among the 105 participants who indicated that the research software they work on is part of a project (**Figure 13**), 95 provided additional detail about how that project is funded (**Figure 14**). For those who indicated that their software is project-based, we asked how the project is funded. **Figure 14** shows that funding sources vary considerably. The most frequently selected option was Part of a project that is funded through other means ($n = 28$), followed by Part of a project that is funded through NWO ($n = 23$). Notably, 18 participants said they do not know if or how their project is funded, while others reported support from EU research programs ($n = 16$) and the eScience Center ($n = 14$). A small group ($n = 6$) stated that their software is developed in a project that receives no funding at all.

Figure 14. Funding sources for software projects (Question 9).

To better understand the *other means* category, we analyzed the *free-text* responses submitted by participants who selected that option. As shown in **Table 8**, these responses reveal a range of funding models, including “institutional” or “internal university support”, “mixed or patchwork funding from various projects”, and combinations of known funders such as EU programs and the eScience Center. This reinforces the idea that research software is often supported through diverse and non-standard funding structures, and that clear categorization is not always possible from the researcher’s perspective.

In summary, while most participants develop research software within funded projects, the landscape of funding awareness and attribution is complex. A notable share of participants either do not know how their work is funded or describe situations where support comes indirectly, from evolving or blended sources.

As a follow-up to **Question 9**, we asked participants whose software is *not part of a project* or who did not know how the project is funded to clarify their understanding of the funding situation. **Question 9.1** gave these respondents three choices: “I know how it is funded,” “I have an idea,” and “I do not know.” The results, shown in **Figure 15**, indicate that 10 participants (50%) expressed *clear confidence* in their knowledge of how the work is funded. An equal number of respondents (6 each) were *uncertain* or admitted to having *no knowledge* of funding mechanisms.

Figure 15. Participant awareness of how software is funded when not part of a known project.

Participants who said they knew how the work is funded shared a diverse range of funding models, as visualized in **Figure 16**. Their responses included salaries, leftover from other projects, not having a specific funding, “the first money stream of universities”, and non-project-based mechanisms such as PhD stipends or a general staff position that includes software work.

Figure 16. Reported funding types among those who know how their software is funded.

Those who indicated they had an idea but were not sure (**Figure 17**) also described varied sources. Responses included “group or institute budgets”, “Institute funding/ national growth fund”, “first money stream of university”, and combinations of formal and informal support. A few explicitly stated that they are not directly funded to work on the software and contribute to it in their free time.

Figure 17. Gessed or partial awareness of funding sources (Question 9.1).

Taken together, **Questions 9** and **9.1** reveal a nuanced funding landscape. While the majority of participants in **Question 9** reported working within clearly funded projects, **Question 9.1** highlights the *informal* and *indirect* pathways through which software work is often supported — especially for those working outside of explicit projects.

In **Question 10**, we asked participants to voluntarily share the name of the project or grant that supports the research software they work with. Although this question was optional and *open-ended*, many participants responded. In total, 35 participants disclosed at least one project or grant name. The responses, shown in **Table 9**, reveal a mix of specific grant titles, institutional references, and non-specific or placeholder entries.

Table 2. Project and grant names disclosed by participants in Question 10.

Question 10 - Grants that fund projects where a research software is developed
Horizon2020
27022G16
Riken
NLESC.CIT2021.002
Onderzoek op Routes door Consortia 2018
NLESC.OEC.2021.026
ESI-FAR (NWO)
Open eScience Call
NLESC.CIT.2021.006
ODISSEI
17600
PSSC style contract with SKA Organisation (SKAO)
Euratom Research and Training Programme Grant Agreement No 101052200
NOVA
NLESC.OEC.2023.017
EU Grant 101119830
CONACYT-Alianza FiiDEM (Reference: 2019- 000005-01EXTF-0027)
NWO-STW/AES
Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101093934
ERC starter RECEPT, ERC starter ALPaCa, NWO ASDI GAHTIe
BIGDG.PREV.2018.012
184035004
2022.025 - Snellius
ERC
NWO
Simulating the Ruisdael Observatory
ERC
EU Horizon under grant agreement no. 101070014.
Various national funding agencies
27024S01
Zurich Instruments
FS6: TruBlo Open Call 3
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Networks
NLESC.OEC.2021.032
EU H2020
Open eScience Call
ALWGO.2018.036
NWO-Kleine
ALMA development study (ESO)
Horizon 2020 No 101004110
TTW Smart Industry grant
101004719
VI.C.182.011
EuroHPC
NWO
Horizon Europe No 101004110
NLESC.OEC.2023.008
Netherlands Institute for Conservation+Art+Science+ Small Project Grant
NLESC.SSIML.2022c.025
eScience Center
OpenSSI 2022a
JTFN-00052

027.020.G06
101131550
Horizon Europe
ESA / EUSPA
NWO Open Competition Domain Science-M
NLESC.CIT.2022.006
Open ODISSEI-eScience
Tii
OpenSSI 2021b
ERC ESCADA
Several countries investing
Joint CSER and eScience programme
eScience Center/Surf
Many

Some grants and funders were mentioned more than once. For example, the Open eScience Call appeared twice, and NWO, ERC, eScience Center, or SURF were each mentioned at least **once** in either full or abbreviated form. In several cases, participants indicated they had received funding through multiple grants or projects, using terms like “many” or “multiple grants over time” (3 mentions). Others provided only a project number or an identifier, without the grant’s formal name, making exact categorization more difficult.

A notable number of entries (6 responses with "None", and 5 with "-") suggest that some participants chose not to disclose funding details or did not consider the software work to be directly tied to a named project.

4.4 Budget Allocation and Financial Sustainability

Sustaining research software requires not only technical and human effort but also dedicated *financial support*. This section explores how software maintenance is (or is not) funded across projects and institutions. It is based on responses to **Questions 11 through 16**, which were shown conditionally depending on earlier answers—particularly whether the software was part of a structured or funded project. These questions address the availability of dedicated budgets, participant awareness of financial mechanisms, institutional practices, and how maintenance costs are accounted for.

Maintenance budgeting within projects

The survey responses highlight significant challenges in securing dedicated funding for software maintenance, both during project planning and after project completion. **Questions 11, 12, and 13** were shown only to participants who indicated in **Question 9** that their research software was part of a funded project. **Question 14** was shown only to those who answered *Yes* to **Question 13**. Similarly, **Questions 15 and 16** were shown only to participants who indicated that some form of funding existed in **Questions 11 and 12**. As a result, the number of responses to these questions reflects a filtered subset of participants—not the full survey population

As shown in **Figure 18**, only 11% of the respondents reported that their projects *include a specific maintenance budget during the project*, meaning that during the planning phase of the project, there was awareness for the required maintenance costs. In contrast, the majority (65%) indicated that *no dedicated budget for research software maintenance was included in the project*. A small group reported that maintenance was supported by alternative sources outside the project funding, such as internal institutional funds, the *eScience Center*, or collaborations like *CERN* and *the LHCb collaboration*. It is worth noting that ~6% of the respondents indicated that the research software that is part of their project does not require maintenance.

The *Other* responses (see **Table 8** in [Appendix 1](#)) suggest that in the absence of formal maintenance budgets, participants often *rely on ad hoc or project-specific workarounds, or treat software development as voluntary labor*. This highlights a broader issue: *software sustainability often depends on individual initiative or informal institutional flexibility rather than dedicated structural funding*.

Figure 18. Whether a project includes a dedicated budget for software maintenance.

These findings point to a key vulnerability: even when software is developed within structured and funded research projects, *maintenance is rarely planned or explicitly resourced*. Funding is often pieced together *from future projects, borrowed from other sources, or not considered at all—either because it is overlooked by applicants or not allowed within the grant*. This echoes findings from **Question 5**, where participants reported spending relatively little time on maintenance tasks, despite its central importance to long-term software sustainability.

Figure 19. Availability of budget for post-project software maintenance.

The survey also asked whether a dedicated maintenance budget was planned for after the end of the project (**Question 12**). After the project ends, 38% of the respondents pointed out that *there was no budget available for maintaining the research software* (**Figure 19**). Most respondents (21%) either rely on future grant applications or expect the community to maintain the software (27%). Only 13% of participants indicated that dedicated or alternative post-project funds are available for maintenance. Relying on future grants or community support strongly suggests that no dedicated budget has been allocated for maintaining the research software after the project

ends. These results altogether reflect a *significant gap in continuity planning* for software sustainability after a research project ends.

Among those who have funding for maintenance (**Figure 20**), most (n=3) use it to assign maintenance tasks to existing personnel, and only one respondent used it to hire dedicated staff.

Q15: How is the funding available for maintaining the software code used?

Figure 20. How maintenance funds are used when available (e.g., staff assignment or hiring).

Finally, participants were asked how much of the project budget is actually allocated to maintenance (**Figures 21 and 22**). The majority (70%) did not know, while the rest provided a specific percentage. Most of these percentage-based responses were very low, with ~76% of respondents indicating 0%, emphasizing the minimal financial attention research software maintenance receives in practice. This result appears inconsistent with responses to **Questions 11 and 12**, as **Question 16** was only shown to participants who indicated that some form of maintenance funding existed—either planned during the project or intended after its completion. One possible interpretation is that maintenance was considered during planning, but not explicitly written into the project budget.

Q16: How much of the project budget is reserved for software maintenance?

Figure 21. Participant awareness of how much of the project budget is allocated to maintenance.

Q16: Reported Percentage of Project Budget Allocated to Maintenance

Figure 22. Reported percentage of the project budget allocated to maintenance.

Institutional budget structures

The absence of long-term planning is further underscored in responses to **Question 13**, which asked whether the participant's organization has a dedicated maintenance budget at the institutional level. As seen in **Figure 23**, 72% of the respondents answered *negatively*, indicated that *there was no budget dedicated to software maintenance in their institution*. Similar to the results of **Question 12**, 14% rely on other budget resources for software maintenance. Surprisingly still 14% of the respondents indicated that their institution has a dedicated budget for maintenance. Overall, these results suggest that even when software is maintained beyond the project, *there is no consistent mechanism to fund that maintenance*.

Q13: Is there a dedicated organizational budget for maintaining research software?

Figure 23. Whether the organization has a dedicated software maintenance budget.

To further explore the institutional budget structure, **Question 14** asked those who said there was no maintenance budget to elaborate. Their responses, shown in **Figure 24**, reveal that 32% of respondents *do not know why there isn't any dedicated budget in their institution*. The remainder either have some idea or report knowing the reason with certainty.

Figure 24. Participant awareness of why there is no maintenance budget.

To better understand the reasons behind this lack of funding in the institutions, we examined the *free-text* responses provided by those who indicated they knew or partially knew the reason. These were thematically grouped into broader categories such as *Funding Issues*, *Policy Gaps*, and *Academic Priorities* shown in **Figure 25**. Specific answers for each category are given in [Appendix 1, Table 10](#).

Figure 25. Grouped reasons for lack of dedicated maintenance budgets.

When grouped into conceptual themes, the most frequently mentioned barrier is related to funding issues (31%), including responses that emphasized the *dominance of project-based funding models, the lack of follow-up grants, and structural limitations in Dutch or European funding schemes*. Close behind were academic priorities, where participants highlighted a *lack of academic incentives, career recognition, or the perception that software maintenance is not “scientific” work*. Institutional barriers, such as *internal policy gaps or unclear responsibilities*, and Policy Gaps, such as the *absence of long-term planning or budget foresight*, were also significant. These results reveal that the absence of maintenance budgets is not due to a single issue, but rather a combination of systemic challenges across funding structures, academic culture, and institutional frameworks.

Post-project budget expectations across research fields

We looked at how expectations for post-project research software maintenance funding vary across scientific domains (**Figure 26**).

Figure 26. Expectations for post-project maintenance funding by research field (Question 2 vs Question 12).

Key observations are

- Across most fields, the dominant response is **“No budget available after the project”** — highlighting the fragility of long-term software support.
- Several respondents in **Astronomy & Astrophysics**, **Physics**, and **Computer Science & AI** expect that **new grants will be written** to support software maintenance. This suggests a reliance on follow-up funding cycles rather than built-in project budgeting.
- A small number of respondents — notably in **Astronomy & Astrophysics** — report either **reserved funds from their project budget** or **other available funds** for post-project maintenance.
- Interestingly, some in **Interdisciplinary & Cross-Domain** and **Environmental Sciences** expect the **community of users** to take over maintenance responsibilities, indicating a decentralized, collaborative approach.

Research fields and the availability of dedicated budgets for research software

Figure 27 reveals striking disparities across research domains in terms of budgetary support for software sustainability.

Figure 27. Heatmap of software maintenance budget availability by research field (Question 2 vs Question 13).

The total number of participants shown for each research field in this heatmap (**Question 2 vs. Question 13**) does not match the full counts from **Question 2** alone. This discrepancy is due to the survey flow logic: **Question 13** was not shown to all respondents — only to those who followed a specific path or met certain conditions earlier in the survey. The most common response across nearly all fields was:

“No, there is no budget specified for software maintenance,” suggesting that structured, predictable funding mechanisms are lacking.

Notably:

- **Astronomy & Astrophysics** stands out, with **5 respondents confirming the existence of a dedicated budget**, and **12 indicating another budget is used**. This may reflect the domain’s long-standing reliance on complex and collaborative software infrastructures.
- **Computer Science & AI** and **Earth & Environmental Sciences** also show a small number of “Yes” responses, but these are exceptions.
- Disciplines such as **Mathematics & Computational Science, Interdisciplinary & Cross-Domain**, and **Life Sciences & Medicine** consistently indicate a lack of dedicated budgets — despite heavy dependence on research software in these domains.

This suggests that while software is critical across scientific disciplines, **formal budgetary recognition remains inconsistent**. Even in fields with heavy software reliance, organizational support structures appear underdeveloped. This suggests a gap between software use and institutional planning. Taken together, the **Question 2 – Question 12** and **Question 2–Question 13** analyses reveal a double vulnerability: research software often lacks both institutional support and structured follow-up funding, even in fields where software is a foundational tool. This dual absence of support points to a systemic gap in research software sustainability planning

4.5 Human Resources and Maintenance Responsibilities

In this section, we explore who is responsible for maintaining research software, and whether this responsibility is formally recognized in job descriptions or supported with dedicated time.

Questions 17 to 20 were designed to capture the extent to which software maintenance is embedded in institutional roles, the career stages of those performing this work, and how much of their contract time is actually allocated to it. These insights are essential to understanding whether maintenance is treated as a sustained institutional commitment or left to informal labor.

Q17: Are the people responsible for maintaining the research software you work on explicitly tasked with this responsibility in their job description or annual work plan?

Figure 28. Whether maintenance is part of participants' formal job descriptions.

As shown in **Figure 28**, 60% of respondents indicated there are no individuals explicitly tasked with software maintenance in their job description or work plan. This means that those responsible for maintaining research software often do so without a formal mandate. A smaller group responded “Yes,” suggesting that some institutions or projects do include maintenance responsibilities in official role descriptions. Notably, a portion of respondents answered “I don’t know,” reflecting possible ambiguity or lack of transparency about how responsibilities are assigned.

These results reinforce earlier findings (e.g., **Question 5** and **Question 13**) showing that maintenance is frequently under-prioritized. When tasks are not contractually defined, they are at greater risk of being deprioritized or unsupported, particularly when project funding ends or staff roles change.

Question 18 highlights the wide range of software maintenance responsibility among the respondents (**Figure 29**).

- The main responses show that PhD students, postdocs, and software engineers are the most common maintainers. These are often non-permanent or technical roles, raising sustainability concerns. See **Table 11** for grouped career stages.
- A notable portion of participants selected or described “Multiple career stages”, especially in *free-text* answers (**Figure 30**). These included phrases like “*whoever has time/need*” or “*mix of postdocs and permanent staff*”, pointing to an ad hoc or shared maintenance culture.
- Tenured staff, while present, are less represented than expected given their institutional permanence and leadership potential.

Q18: What is the career stage or job title of the individuals responsible for maintaining the research software you work with?

Figure 29. Career stages of individuals responsible for software maintenance.

Q18: Other

Figure 30. Free-text responses about maintenance roles across career stages.

This distribution suggests that while software maintenance is widespread, it is often informally shared rather than strategically assigned. Without clearer ownership and role definition, long-term sustainability may depend more on individual initiative than institutional planning.

The responses to **Question 19** provide important insight into the lack of clarity and formality around the allocation of contract time for software maintenance.

- As illustrated in **Figure 31**, 70% of participants do not know how much time is officially allocated for maintenance in their contracts. This aligns with earlier findings from **Question 17**, where most participants reported that maintenance duties are not formally included in job descriptions.

- Among those who do know, most report very low allocation percentages of their contract time (**Figure 32**). Specifically, 18 participants said 0%, and only a handful reported values over 20%.
- Combined with the responses to **Question 18**, which showed that maintenance is often handled by PhDs, postdocs, or “whoever has time,” these data further support the conclusion that maintenance is performed informally and is rarely institutionally structured.
- The non-numeric responses (“varies” and “voluntary”) reinforce this pattern, suggesting maintenance work is opportunistic rather than planned (**Table 12**).

Q19: How much of the contract time of the individuals responsible for maintaining the research software you work with is allocated for software maintenance?

Figure 31. Contracted time allocated to software maintenance (as reported by participants).

Q19: Percentage of Contract Time for Software Maintenance

Figure 32. Actual time participants spend on software maintenance.

Taken together, this question highlights a critical gap between the need for long-term software maintenance and the institutional mechanisms meant to support it. When contract time is undefined or untracked, it becomes difficult to plan, justify, or fund this labor, even though it is foundational to research reproducibility and infrastructure.

While **Question 19** focused on how much time is *formally allocated* in contracts or work plans, **Question 20** turns to the *actual time* participants report spending on software maintenance in practice.

Figure 33 shows that just over half of the respondents (52 out of 100 participants) reported not knowing how much of their actual working time is dedicated to research software maintenance.

The remaining 48 participants indicated that they did know, and among them, 44 provided numeric estimates that are visualized in **Figure 34**.

Q20: Do you know how much of the actual time is spent on software maintenance?

Figure 33. Awareness of how much time is actually spent on software maintenance.

These responses show that actual time spent on maintenance is often significant: many reported dedicating between 10% and 20% of their time, with a noticeable number also indicating higher percentages such as 30%, 40%, or even 50%. No one reported spending 0%, and one participant reported dedicating their entire working time (100%) to maintenance. Non-numeric responses (**Table 13**) suggest informal or flexible arrangements consistent with those found in **Question 19**.

Q20: Actual Percentage of Time Spent on Software Maintenance

Figure 34. Reported percentage of actual working time spent on software maintenance.

These findings contrast sharply with the results of **Question 19**, where most participants reported 0% formally allocated contract time. Together, the responses to **Questions 19** and **20** suggest a consistent pattern: although software maintenance is rarely embedded in formal workload structures, it is still performed — often extensively — as part of researchers' *actual working time*.

The combined results from **Questions 17** to **20** reveal a consistent and striking pattern: while research software maintenance is essential and ongoing, it is rarely formalized or institutionally supported. These findings suggest that research software maintenance is a hidden but vital layer of academic work — performed, but not planned, and recognized in practice, but not on paper. This

mismatch has implications for sustainability: when maintenance depends on informal effort, it risks being deprioritized, especially during transitions, funding gaps, or staff turnover. The results highlight a need for institutions to formally recognize, allocate time for, and support software maintenance if it is to be sustainable.

Field-specific trends in software maintenance workload

To close this section, we examined how responsibility and time spent on research software maintenance vary across disciplinary domains. **Figure 35** compares, by research field, the proportion of respondents whose job descriptions formally include software maintenance, the average percentage of contracted time allocated to it, and the actual time participants reported spending on this task.

Figure 35. Field-specific trends in software maintenance workload, showing the share of participants explicitly tasked with software maintenance, the average contracted time allocated to this task, and the actual average time spent on it, grouped by research field (Question2vs Question 17, 19 and 20).

The results show notable disparities across domains. Participants in *Astronomy & Astrophysics* report the *highest actual time spent on maintenance* (32%), paired with *relatively high formal assignment* (35%) and moderate contract allocation (24%). In contrast, *Earth & Environmental Sciences* show the *highest average contract allocation* (60%) but a *lower share of formal role recognition* (19%), suggesting that maintenance may be supported through funding structures without being explicitly part of job roles.

Fields such as *Computer Science*, *Chemistry*, and *Engineering* demonstrate a marked gap: maintenance work is reported to occur despite almost no formal role recognition or contract allocation. This underlines how software maintenance often remains an invisible, informal task, especially in domains where such work is critical but undervalued institutionally.

These findings reinforce the systemic issue highlighted throughout Section 4.5: the disconnect between software maintenance responsibilities and institutional structures. For instance, in *Computer Science & AI*, participants reported spending on average 10% of their time on software maintenance, yet none had this work reflected in their contract time and only 23% were explicitly tasked with it. Similarly, in *Engineering & Technology*, 8.5% of time was spent on maintenance, but 0% had any contract allocation or formal responsibility. Even in fields with strong funding

frameworks, such as Earth & Environmental Sciences, where 60% contract time was reported, only 19% of participants had maintenance as a formal task. These consistent mismatches across disciplines show that software maintenance remains an informal and undervalued task, even where it is essential and ongoing.

4.6 Recognition

This section explores how the maintenance of research software is recognized, valued, and supported within institutions. While previous sections addressed funding, staffing, and time allocation, here we examine how participants perceive the cultural and structural importance of maintenance — from institutional reward systems to career advancement and external funding mechanisms. **Questions 21 to 26** provide insight into both the challenges of gaining recognition and the potential interest in new solutions.

In **Question 21**, we asked participants to rank the biggest challenges concerning the maintenance and dissemination of research software (**Figure 36**). Each response had an importance score ranging from 1 (not important) to 5 (extremely important). The goal was to identify which barriers researchers perceive as most significant — and how strongly they feel about them.

Q21: What do you consider to be the biggest challenges concerning the maintenance and dissemination of research software?

Figure 36. Grouped challenge categories concerning research software maintenance (importance scores).

Given the *free-text* nature of the responses, we manually cleaned and grouped the answers into a set of recurring thematic categories, such as *Funding Issues*, *Recognition*, *Documentation*, and *Sustainability*. Similar or related entries were merged — for example, “no long-term funding,” “budget gaps,” and “lack of grants” were all categorized under *Funding Issues*. Responses that did not fit any consistent group were labeled as *Other* and are excluded from the main plot but will be summarized separately. See **Table 14** for the answers grouped by similarity.

Figure 36 displays the grouped challenge categories by the number of mentions (bar length) and their total importance score. This provides insight into both how often each category was mentioned and how strongly participants rated its impact.

The most frequently mentioned challenge was *Funding Issues*, cited 30 times with a combined importance score of 234 — making it the most significant concern by both frequency and weight. It was followed by Sustainability, Recognition, and Time Constraints. Practical challenges such as Documentation, Skill Gaps, and Training & Support were also identified but received slightly lower scores. Notably, *Infrastructure* had the fewest mentions and lowest importance score overall.

These findings resonate closely with earlier results from the survey. In **Question 19**, participants were asked how much of their contract time is formally allocated for maintenance, and the most common answer was 0%. In **Question 20**, which asked about actual working time spent on maintenance, most participants reported spending significant time—often between 10% and 25%—despite having no formal allocation. This mismatch between formal responsibilities and actual practice is echoed in the prominence of *Time Constraints* and *Recognition* as major challenges in **Question 21**. Participants are clearly spending time on maintenance, but without a formal setup.

In addition to the grouped categories shown in **Figure 36**, several participants provided *free-text* responses that did not clearly align with any predefined category. These entries, while diverse, offer valuable insights into individual perspectives on research software challenges. Some focused on **technical or design issues**, such as “*instability of Python*,” “*maintainability in general*,” and “*size of scope*.” Others highlighted broader strategic concerns like “*making the software well-known*” or “*focus*.” Although each of these was mentioned only once, their presence suggests that beyond institutional and funding barriers, researchers also struggle with software visibility, architecture, and adoption, which can complicate long-term maintenance and impact. These more niche responses complement the major themes without contradicting them, highlighting that the landscape of maintenance challenges is not only structural, but also technical and conceptual.

Q22: Is consideration given to work on research software in the career decisions of those involved in its development (including yourself)?

Figure 37. Free-text responses highlighting additional maintenance challenges.

In **Question 22**, participants were asked whether the development of the software they work with is considered in the career decisions. How participants perceive the recognition of research software development in career evaluation processes is presented in **Figure 37**. The most common response, selected by 44 participants, was that development is valued, but maintenance is not. An additional 28 participants said that both development and maintenance are recognized, while 19

indicated that neither is valued in career decisions. Only one respondent reported the inverse — that maintenance is valued while development is not — a rare exception.

A small but notable group (eight participants) selected *Other*, and their explanations suggest a mix of uncertainty, ambiguity, and inconsistent practices. Several respondents explicitly stated that they did not know or found the question unclear, while others remarked that recognition varies widely depending on factors such as funding source, contract type, or institute. One participant reflected on grading a Master’s thesis and noted the inability to reward software quality in academic evaluation, underscoring how software maintenance often remains peripheral even in performance-based settings.

These answers mirrors the findings from **Question 21**, where lack of recognition emerged as one of the top-rated challenges to sustainable software practices. It also aligns with earlier results from **Question 17**, where most respondents indicated that maintenance responsibilities are not formally stated in job descriptions or work plans. Moreover, **Question 18** showed that maintenance is widely distributed across various roles, including PhDs and postdocs — groups whose work is highly dependent on career evaluations.

When broken down by research field, the responses to **Question 22** revealed clear disciplinary differences in how software work is recognized in career evaluations. In many domains — particularly in astronomy, physics, and mathematics — participants reported that software development is valued more than maintenance. This aligns with the broader theme seen across the survey: while novel development is often tied to publication output and institutional prestige, the long-term effort required to sustain software tends to be overlooked. Only a few fields, such as computer science and environmental sciences, reported more balanced recognition of both development and maintenance.

Q23: Do the people working on the maintenance of the research software you work with (including yourself) write hours in a financial administrative system?

Figure 38. Whether participants or their colleagues write hours for maintenance in financial systems.

To better understand the administrative handling of research software maintenance, participants were first asked in **Question 23** whether the people responsible for maintenance — including themselves — *write hours in a financial administrative system*. This was intended to assess whether such work is formally tracked, for example in grant reporting or internal timekeeping tools.

As shown in **Figure 38**, responses were fairly evenly distributed: 45 participants selected either 'Yes' or 'No', while 10 selected "I do not know." This split indicates that in many cases, maintenance

is still handled informally or without institutional time-tracking structures, while in others, it is at least partially recorded.

Q24: How do the people working on the maintenance of the research software you work with (including yourself) write hours in a financial administrative system?

Figure 39. How logged hours for software maintenance are administratively categorized.

Based on survey logic, only those who answered "Yes" were shown **Question 24**, which asked *how* the hours are logged in systems where this occurs. According to **Figure 39**, the most common response (17 participants) was that hours are recorded under a project label associated with "research (or similar)." Another 9 respondents said "I do not know," suggesting that while hours may be logged, the administrative labeling is not always visible to the person doing the work. A smaller number (eight participants) reported logging hours under "engineering (or similar)" within the project label, while a few others selected *other project or post* labels not tied directly to research or engineering.

These findings highlight several key points. First, consistent with **Question 19**, even when hours are tracked, they are often not specifically allocated for maintenance in contracts. Second, echoing **Question 17**, where maintenance duties were frequently not included in job descriptions, this tracking — when it happens — seems to rely on general-purpose project categories rather than dedicated funding lines or role definitions. Finally, the ambiguity reflected in "I do not know" responses across both questions reinforces that software maintenance, while essential, is still administratively invisible in many institutions.

The administrative categorization also reveals a potential tension: if software maintenance is written under generic research or engineering posts, its true cost is hidden, and its importance may be underestimated in financial reporting and planning.

Q25: Does your organization measure the value or impact of research software?

Figure 40. Institutional methods used to measure research software value or impact.

As part of our investigation into institutional recognition of research software, we asked participants whether they were aware of any way their organization uses to measure the value or impact of the software developed there. **Question 25** was designed to reveal whether such evaluations exist and, if so, what types of metrics or indicators are used. Participants could select multiple predefined options and were also invited to provide additional detail through a *free-text* response. Results are shown in **Figure 40**.

Because respondents could choose multiple answers, the results are presented as total response counts rather than individual participant counts. As shown in **Figure 40**, each bar represents the number of times a given method was selected across all responses. To make the plot more readable, long answer labels were simplified.

Before plotting, we processed the raw data to handle formatting inconsistencies caused by multi-line responses. These included splitting answer strings, recombining fragmented text, and grouping responses by meaning — for example, answers referencing government or commercial use were grouped under “*Measured via external adoption.*” *Free-text* responses such as “measured in another way” were retained as a separate category, and responses that didn't clearly match predefined options were excluded.

The most frequently selected method was “*Measured via external adoption*”, with 41 mentions. This included indicators such as whether the software is used by governments, companies, or external academic groups. This was followed closely by “*Not measured*” (39 mentions) and “*Measured via citations to papers*” (38 mentions), suggesting that while many institutions do use some form of evaluation, a significant number still do not — or only assess software indirectly through academic publication metrics.

Other responses in this category included “*Measured via software downloads*” and “*Measured via number of users*”, both of which reflect technical reach or scale of use. 13 participants selected “*Measured in another way*”, and their *free-text* explanations showed a wide range of informal indicators, including GitHub stars, forks, or contribution activity, awareness within the research community, or participation in workshops and user groups.

While the specific methods varied, most responses centered on evidence of usage or external impact — whether through citations, downloads, user base size, or adoption beyond the

originating research group. Even the responses categorized under “measured in another way” echoed this theme, referencing GitHub statistics and anecdotal reach as informal markers of value. Together, these results show that when software is evaluated, it is usually through indirect signals of visibility and uptake, rather than through metrics that reflect long-term maintenance, reliability, or sustainability.

Final reflection from participants

At the end of the survey, participants were given the opportunity to provide any additional remarks related to the topics discussed or about the survey itself. A total of 27 respondents used this space to share extended thoughts, concerns, and contextual details that go beyond predefined answer categories. These *free-text* comments offer valuable insight into the lived experience of those involved in research software development and maintenance. Several clear themes emerged across these responses.

Many participants emphasized the systemic funding and career challenges tied to software maintenance. They described a persistent struggle to secure long-term support and highlighted a disconnect between short project cycles and the continuous nature of maintaining software. Several respondents noted that funding, when available, often ends with the developer’s contract—typically a PhD or postdoc—with no clear succession plan in place. This lack of continuity was repeatedly characterized as unsustainable, with one respondent explicitly linking the pressure and lack of support to burnout.

Closely related were reflections on the lack of institutional recognition for maintenance activities, especially in contrast to the weight placed on academic publishing. Some respondents reported that time spent on code was seen as secondary or even detrimental to their perceived academic value, particularly in traditional disciplinary environments. The contrast between valuable community contributions and formal career incentives was noted by multiple PhDs, software engineers, and project leads.

A number of comments also raised the diversity of roles, funding models, and use cases not fully captured by the survey. Some participants worked as freelancers or outside standard Dutch academic frameworks. Others noted that their software was intended for limited or one-time use and thus didn’t fit assumptions about long-term sustainability. Several indicated that they had to guess on certain survey questions because the predefined answers didn’t reflect their situation or because they lacked insight into institutional processes like hour logging or evaluation.

Other responses pointed to technical and structural barriers to sustainability, including platform obsolescence, poor documentation practices, and a lack of shared tools across institutions. One participant noted the risk of commercial or streaming-only software becoming unusable when platforms are shut down, threatening long-term reproducibility. Others called for shared infrastructure — such as centralized electronic lab notebooks — and more opportunities for community coordination.

Despite these challenges, several respondents expressed gratitude for the survey itself, describing it as timely and necessary. A few offered specific suggestions, such as the need for clearer role definitions, maintenance handover protocols, and regular evaluations to ensure that software remains usable and supported.

As a result, the responses to **Question 26** reinforce the survey’s broader findings: while research software is widely recognized as essential, the organizations that support its long-term value — funding, recognition, administrative structure, and sustainability planning — remain uneven and underdeveloped. These open comments serve as a powerful reminder that efforts to improve research software sustainability must be informed not only by metrics, but by the voices of those doing the work.

Beyond individual questions, several cross-sectional comparisons reveal important patterns. For example, differences in how software contributions are recognized (**Question 22**) or measured (**Question 25**) are not evenly distributed across disciplines: fields such as Computer Science and Earth Sciences appear more likely to track or value these efforts, while others, like Physics or Life Sciences, often report limited recognition or awareness. Similarly, the individuals tasked with software maintenance (**Question 18**) vary by field—ranging from PhD students in Life Sciences to dedicated research software engineers in Astronomy or Mathematics.

5. Conclusions

The survey results provide a comprehensive view of the current state of research software development and sustainability within the NES domain in the Netherlands. Each subsection of the results ([Section 4](#)) reveals different aspects of this ecosystem—when brought together, they highlight recurring themes of informality, lack of structural support, and dependency on individual effort.

Participant profiles and roles

The majority of participants are affiliated with universities and represent a wide range of research fields. They often fulfill multiple roles—developing, using, maintaining, and managing research software simultaneously. While development and use occupy the largest share of work time, maintenance activities consistently receive the least attention, both in terms of time and formal role definition. This imbalance points to a systemic under-prioritization of maintenance efforts, despite their importance to software sustainability.

Context and use

Most research software is developed with broader use in mind—by a research group or scientific community. It also covers multiple types, from specific tools to core infrastructure. This shows that software developed in NES is not purely individual, but part of collective research output. Yet, this broader intent is not matched by sustainable support structures.

Project and funding awareness

Software development is mostly embedded in funded research projects, but many respondents are unaware of how this funding is structured. Maintenance is often not taken into account. Funding sources are diverse, often described as “patchwork,” and lack consistent categories. A portion of respondents report no funding at all, or contribute in their spare time. Grants named suggest dependence on NWO, EU, and eScience Center, but transparency and clarity are lacking.

Budget allocation and financial sustainability

Maintenance is rarely budgeted for—either during or after the project ends. Only a minority of respondents report having specific maintenance budgets, and even fewer indicate organizational-level funding. When funds are available, they are mostly used to reassign existing personnel rather than hiring new staff. Participants often do not know why maintenance is unfunded, reflecting both structural and communication issues. This finding reinforces the hidden nature of maintenance costs and the vulnerability of software after the end of a project.

Human resources and maintenance responsibilities

Few participants report that software maintenance is explicitly part of job descriptions. The task often falls to PhD students, postdocs, or anyone available, rather than being formally assigned. Contractual time allocated to maintenance is minimal or unknown, yet actual time spent can be significant indicating a disconnect between practice and formal planning. Maintenance is performed, but informally and without structural safeguards, suggesting a reliance on goodwill and individual dedication.

Field-specific differences in maintenance workload planning also emerged. In Astronomy & Astrophysics, participants reported relatively high formal responsibility (35%) and significant actual maintenance time (32%). In contrast, participants in Computer Science & AI and Engineering & Technology reported no formal time allocation and little or no contract recognition, despite spending meaningful time on maintenance. This highlights a systemic disparity between disciplines, reinforcing the need for domain-sensitive policy solutions.

Recognition

Participants identify funding, sustainability, and lack of recognition as the biggest challenges to software maintenance. Many report that development work is recognized more than maintenance in career decisions. Hour logging is inconsistent and, when tracked, is usually recorded under generic research posts, not maintenance-specific categories, making the work administratively invisible. Measurement of software impact, when it occurs, is mostly informal and based on usage indicators like downloads or citations. A substantial number of participants report no evaluation or awareness of how software impact is assessed. The open comments confirm these trends, voicing frustration about short-termism, lack of career rewards, and structural neglect.

Final reflection

- Results point to organizational invisibility of development and maintenance of research software.
- The maintenance of software is widespread and time-consuming yet remains structurally unsupported.
- Recognition and funding are inconsistent, often relying on individual initiative and ad hoc arrangements.
- To bridge this gap, both research organizations and funders must integrate research software development and maintenance into career systems, budgeting processes, and infrastructure planning.
- Sustainability strategies must account for disciplinary norms, institutional structures, and informal practices, which vary significantly across the NES domain. Field-specific results reveal that these structural differences are not evenly distributed. In Astronomy & Astrophysics, participants reported relatively high levels of formal recognition and time allocation for maintenance tasks, alongside high actual time spent. In contrast, fields such as Computer Science and Engineering showed little to no formal assignment or contract time, despite ongoing maintenance work. These patterns suggest that any effective policy or funding response must be sensitive not only to the technical nature of research software, but also to the disciplinary culture and institutional incentives that shape how maintenance is assigned, resourced, and recognized.

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This work is part of a broader effort to increase the visibility, sustainability, and recognition of research software within the Dutch academic system.

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Appendix 1 – Categorized Responses

This appendix lists all grouped or simplified response categories applied to *open-ended* or multi-response survey questions. See [Section 3](#) for a description of the grouping method.

Table 3. Other institution types reported in Question 1.

Question 1- Type of Institutions Participants Work In - Other	Free text answers given by participants
Open Source project with own governance	
Self-employed research software engineer	
JIVE ERIC	
UMC	

Table 4. Research field categories grouped by similarity (Question 2).

Question 2- Research field categories grouped by similarity	Free text responses given by the participants
Astronomy & Astrophysics	'astrophysics','Astronomy', 'Astrophysics', 'Radioastronomy', 'astronomy','astronomy, data science', 'Planetary Astrophysics', 'Very Long Baseline Interferometry (radio astronomy technique)', 'Data processing for radio astronomy', 'astronomy and computing', 'Astro', 'Asstrophysics
Physics & Applied Physics	'Physics', 'computational physics', 'physics of granular materials','physics', 'High Energy Physics', 'Fusion', 'plasma physics', 'Fluid dynamics', 'Applied Physics'
Mathematics & Computational Science	'Applied mathematics + scientific computing','Mathematics', 'Applied mathematics', 'Computational mathematics', 'Computational science','Artificial Intelligence', 'Numerical Mathematics', 'Computing Science/Cryptography','Statistics','computer science','mathematics','Applied CS'
Engineering & Technology	'Mechanical Engineering', 'coastal engineering','Natural sciences', 'Design Engineering Science (Industrial Design)', 'Hydroinformatics', 'Civil/Environmental Engineering', 'Sensors and smart systems','Natural Sciences & Engineering'
Computer Science & AI	'Interconnectivity and predictive AI','Computer Science', 'Artificial intelligence', 'Machine Learning','artificial intelligence', 'Data Science', 'privacy and security', 'Information Retrieval', 'High Performance Computing (hpc)', 'open quantum systems','Software Engineering', 'hpc','Software engineering'
Life Sciences & Medicine	'Life sciences', 'Biochemistry', 'Medical Biology', 'Life sciences - biochemistry - Mass Spectrometry', 'Public Health and environment', 'Structural biology/Biochemistry','Bioinformatics', 'Computational Biology', 'Neurosciences', 'Medical Science','life sciences','Biochemistry, biophysics','Chemical biology','Biochemistry '
Earth & Environmental Sciences	'Geosciences', 'Environmental Sciences', 'Earth Observation', 'Environmental Sciences','Environmental Sciences ', 'Hydrology', 'Climate science', 'Industrial Ecology', 'Urban ecology', 'Earth and Environment ', 'Sustainability',

	'Sustainability Sciences', 'Environmental and Geosciences', 'Geo-informatics', 'Earth and Environment', 'Environment and Sustainability'
Chemistry & Material Science	'Chemistry', 'Theoretical Chemistry', 'Physical chemistry', 'chemistry', 'theoretical chemistry', 'Theoretical chemistry', 'Material Discovery', 'Chemical Biology', 'Biochemistry', 'Organic chemistry', 'physical chemistry'
Linguistics & Cognitive Science	'Neurolinguistics', 'Natural Language Processing', 'Formal Logic and Cognitive Science'
Interdisciplinary & Cross-Domain	'cross-domain research', 'Research Data Management', 'research software', 'Research Data Management ', 'Not applicable: central research software management support', 'No Research Field I am support staff', 'Originally Physics, now working in different fields (Physics, Astronomy, History, Medicine, etc.)
Other	'Social sciences', 'Imaging', 'None', 'Journalism Studies', 'Hydrometeorology', "Geoinformation processing applied to water sanitation and health", "all", "applied cryptography", "Energy System Integration", "Granular Materials", "environmental sciences", "NES", "Theoretical Macroecology and ecotoxicology", "hydrology", Symmetric Cryptography", " Fusion Science", "Radar", "Industrial ecology"

Table 5. Free-text job titles provided under *Other* (Question 3).

Question 3 – Job Title	Free-text responses describing alternative job titles
Other	'Instrument Scientist', 'Programme Manager', 'Department Head', 'Research software consultant', 'Research Technician', ' Data Steward', 'Group leader', 'competence group lead', 'product owner', 'information manager', 'senior researcher', 'Principal Researcher & Strategist', 'Research Software Steward', 'Lecturer', 'Research Staff', 'Manager', 'Head of Technical Operations and R&D', 'Section Head', 'Senior Scientist', 'Technology Lead (associate professor equivalent)', ' Researcher', 'Senior Research Software Engineer', 'Scientific staff'

Table 6. Simplified response categories for research software activities (Questions 4 and 5).

Question 4 & 5- Simplified activities concerning research software	Multiple choice answers provided to participants
Develop	Develop research software
Maintain	Maintain research software
Use	Use it as part of my own research
Facilitate/Manage	Facilitate others or manage others to do so
None	None
Other	"Algorithm development", "Understand research user needs and provide advice or recommendations", "Teaching", "acquire, setup, manage and maintain HPC infrastructure", "Contribute to open source projects", "Provide research ideas leading to research software"

Table 7. Roles associated with research software, grouped from free-text and checkbox answers.

Question 8- Simplified activities concerning research software	Multiple choice answers provided to participants
PI or Manager Creating Software	I am the PI, co-PI, supervisor or manager on a project where research software is created
PI or Manager Maintaining Software	I am the PI, co-PI, supervisor or manager on a project where pre-existing research software is maintained
Researcher Developing Software	I am doing research and as part of the research I am developing research software
Researcher Maintaining Software	I am doing research and as part of the research I am maintaining research software
Researcher Using Software	I am doing research and as part of the research I am using research software
Not a Researcher but Writing Software	I am not doing research but I am writing research software

Table 8. Other ways of financing maintenance during projects (Question 11).

Question 11 - Specific part of the project budget reserved for maintaining the research software	Free text responses describing other ways of financing & number of occurrences.+-
Other	'The project partly consists of catching up on maintenance, and partly of adding new features.' 'Budget, but all tied into grants with complex commitments.' 'Yes, for Gaia DPAC, no for GaiaUnlimited', 'Software development for scientific projects is assumed to be voluntary work, it does not play a role in annual job evaluation interviews', "I don't have this information.", "I don't know", 'The budget is flexible. No budget is explicitly reserved for maintenance, but maintenance is implicit in the terms of the grants.' 'No, but we work on (and there is budget for working on) business models that should cover for maintenance'
There is another source	"Internal Software Group", "eScience Center", "CERN/The LHCb collaboration", "internal funding"

Table 9. Free -text project or funding references provided in response to Question 10.

Question 13 - Dedicated organizational budget for maintaining research software	Free text responses describing other ways of financing
No, there is another budget for software maintenance	'Internal ICT Department', "There's a small internal software sustainability budget, but it covers only a small subset of all the software we develop.",

	<p>'we can sometimes apply for small software sustainability/generalisation grants after a project ends', 'Institution base budget', "I don't have this information.", 'Actually, none of the options match our situation; with EC grants we pay a large fraction of our software developers and from the remaining percentage not allocated to EC projects we try to maintain outputs from previous projects', 'CERN/The LHCb collaboration ', 'I have agree a technician in my group 1 day a week do most of maintance. This is a private deal with the University. ', 'internal funding if available', 'base institute budget is applied for maintenance'</p>
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Table 10. Reasons for absence of a software maintenance budget, grouped from free-text input.

Question 14 - Reasons why there is no budget for research software maintenance grouped by based on context*	Free text responses given by the participants
<p>*Free text answers given by the participants given in two options are merged in the analysis.</p> <p>I do not know for sure, but I think I know the reason. I know for sure the reason</p>	
<p>Funding Issues</p>	<p>"Everything is project based, so we continuously need to find new projects", "Our funding (NWO) is not constant, so we cannot allocate a fix amount of budget to maintain software long-term. The best we can do is maintain it during the project.", "grants have finite duration", "For the Gaia mission, maintaining the SW is only funded as long as data processing takes place, after that there is no budget. For GaiaUnlimited, the community is expected to pick up maintaining the SW (no budget was requested and that would probably not have been possible)", "Since almost all funding is project based and there are no calls aimed at software maintenance...", "It is not part of the Dutch standard model (NWO) and not easy to put into EU project proposals either", "The grant will run out and I am looking for follow-up funding for maintenance and further development.", "NWO budget is fixed, the money is spent, period.",</p>

	"Software is developed as part of scientific projects, and project always have an end date."
Institutional Barriers	"Institutional inertia and prioritization.", "Our policy is that it is not our responsibility", "There is no discussion about it, so far", "Budget cuts", "Because I do not ask for it, I just do it as long as I have paid projects.", "I suppose it is considered a standard task of the ICT department as part of the base funding of the institute"
Policy Gaps	"Maintenance after project end is not a consideration in setting the budgets", "Overlooked; hard to define an outcome", "It is still new software and the proposal never accounted for long-term maintenance", "Unclear whether maintenance during or after the project is meant.", "The software package has been maintained and developed for decades by a couple of researchers, but it never got an official budget number."
Academic Priorities	"Software maintenance is not considered scientific; it cannot be used for a PhD thesis", "Writing a research grant that says \"we're going to maintain software\" is not going to build anyone's academic career unless it's attached to a big scientific hardware project.", "I do it as part of my PhD, because I have to use the code and benefit from it working well", "Because we only recently realized that the software has long-term usefulness", "inertia", "Often project plans cannot foresee whether the resulting software will be worth maintaining. It is an emergent property of the project going well.", "Perhaps it is too hard to decide which software to maintain with limited budget", "Maintaining software is not seen as part of science, here are no financial or academic rewards for it", "As long as we keep on using the software, we will also maintain it"

Table 11. Career stages of individuals responsible for research software maintenance.

Question 18- Simplified career stages	Multiple choice answers provided to participants
PhD	PhD student (Dutch: promovendi)
Researcher not part of the academic career track	Researcher (In a university: not part of the academic career track)
Tenured	Assistant, an associate or a full professor on a permanent contract (i.e., "tenured")
Tenure tracker	Assistant professor on a temporary contract (i.e., "tenure tracker")
Research software engineer/developer/programmer	Research software engineer/ developer/ programmer

Other	-
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Table 12. Free-text responses describing the career level of maintainers.

Question 18- Free text answers provided by participants	Number of occurrence
Multiple career stages (PhD, Postdoc, Professor, Software Engineer, etc.)	12
I do not know	2
Scientist/Analyst at TNO, researcher at an Institute, etc	1
Not relevant	1
PhD students and MSc students	1
Technician	1
Everyone in my group helps graduated students who left to industry	1

Table 13. Non-numeric responses provided in Question 19 (contracted maintenance time).

Question 19 – Non-numeric answers	Number of responses
Varies	1
Voluntary	1

Table 14. Non-numeric responses provided in Question 20 (actual maintenance time).

Question 20 – Non-numeric answers	Number of responses
Varies	1
Less than 10%	1

Table 15. Grouped responses about challenges in research software maintenance and its dissemination.

Question 21- Challenges concerning the maintenance and dissemination of research software grouped by based similarity	Free text responses given by the participants
Financial Issues	"funding", "finance", "financial" ,"money", "budget", "resources"
Time Constraints	"time", "lack of time"
Sustainability	"sustainability", "maintenance"
Community Involvement	"community"
Recognition	"recognition", "credit", "acknowledgement"
Documentation	"documentation", "docs"
Skill Gaps	"skills", "expertise", "knowledge"
Training & Support	"training", "support"
Infrastructure	"infrastructure"
Dissemination	"dissemination"

Table 16. Free-text responses regarding recognition of software in career advancement.

Question 22- If consideration is given to work on research software in the career decisions of those involved in its development	Free text answers given by participants
	"Don't know"
	"Hard to say. I noticed when grading an MSc thesis that I wasn't able to give a higher grade because of the quality of the s/w. PhD students should have better employment opportunities"
	"I do not understand the question"
	"Question unclear"
	"unclear; I have not witnessed any such consideration"
	"Both aspects are valued but to varying degrees (from valued to not valued) depending on the funding source, contract type, institute etc "

Table 17. Free-text responses describing how maintenance hours are tracked administratively.

Question 24- How do the people working on the maintenance of the research software write hours in a financial administrative system	Free text answers given by participants
Under project	'No label', 'we don't label projects", 'There are no subcategories: hours are written "under the project" and that's it, no granularity within the project', 'development'
Under post-engineering	'a project that has hours available.'
Under post-research	
Other	'Just labelled "At Work", 'General', 'Indirect hours', 'project currently working on', 'the team'

Table 18. Free-text suggestions for how institutions evaluate or measure software impact.

Question 25- If the organization measures the value or impact of research software - Other	Free text answers given by participants
	'My direct pi guesses at the above no one else tracks it'
	'Citations of the software itself'
	'Number of workshops, courses, presentations'
	'GitHub statistics (stars, forks, etc). I think other ways as well, but not sure'
	'mentions, which can be anything (presentations, news articles, etc.)'
	'Im not sure in which way', 'general awareness of use'
	'pipy installations'
	'if newly implemented method led to a paper'
	"Via 'Pure"
	It is measured informally'
	'We try to go from quantitative measures of impact to more qualitative measures. As an example, the creator of DuckDB is now full professor at our department.'

Appendix 2 – Survey Questions

Q1 What type of institute do you work in? (More than one option can be selected)

- University
- Applied University (Dutch: hogeschool)
- NWO-I Institute (CWI, AMOLF, etc.)
- TO2 Organisation (Deltares, TNO, etc.)
- Government (KNMI, RIVM, PBL, etc.)
- Other Organizations that produce/play a major role in research software in the Netherlands (eScience Center, DANS, SURF)
- Small or Medium Enterprise (less than 50 people)
- Large Enterprise (50 or more people)
- Other (please specify):

Q2 What is your research field?

Q3 What is your title in your institute?

- Professor
- Associate professor
- Assistant professor
- Postdoctoral fellow
- PhD
- MSc student
- Research software engineer
- Software developer
- Data manager
- Other (please specify):

Q4 Which of the following activities concerning research software do you spend your work time on? (More than one option can be selected)

- Develop research software
- Maintain research software
- Facilitate others or manage others to do so
- Use it as part of my own research
- Other

None

Q5 What percentage of your work time do you spend working with research software?

Q6 Regarding the research software you indicated you work with: Is this software developed solely for use in the research of the person who develops it? (This person could be you.) Or is it intended for a research group or community?

Personal use

For a research group or community

Both

Q7 Research software designed for a research group or community is often classified into three types: (T1) Contribution to Community: e.g., PhD students contributing to the software of larger scientific communities. (T2) Core Infrastructure: Research groups introducing novel research infrastructure, where the software becomes one of the infrastructural research services offered to their own group and beyond. (T3) Specific Methods: Software developed for specific experiments, such as controlling hardware, acquiring data, or processing data in specific manners. Does the research software you work on or with fall into any of these categories? (More than one option can be selected.) If not, please indicate how you would classify the research software you work with.

T1: Contribution to Community (1)

T2: Core Infrastructure (2)

T3: Specific Methods (3)

Other (please specify): (4)

Q8 What is your role related to the research software you work with? (More than one option can be selected)

- I am the PI, co-PI, supervisor or manager on a project where research software is created.
- I am the PI, co-PI, supervisor or manager on a project where pre-existing research software is maintained.
- I am doing research and as part of the research I am developing research software.
- I am doing research and as part of the research I am using research software.
- I am doing research and as part of the research I am maintaining research software.
- I am not doing research but I am writing research software.
- Other (please specify):

Q9 Is the research software you work with developed in a specific project? If so, do you know how this project is funded? (If you work on multiple pieces of research software, please answer this question for the project you spend most of your time on).

- Not part of a project.
- Part of a project but I do not know if/how it is funded.
- Part of a project that is not funded.
- Part of a project that is funded through NWO.
- Part of a project that is funded through EU research fund.
- Part of a project that is funded through the eScience Center.
- Part of a project that is funded through other means: (please specify)

Q9.1 Do you know how your work with research software is funded?

- No, I do not know.
- I am not sure but I think it is funded as follows: _____
- I do know, it is funded as follows: _____

Q10 Related to the research software you work with: Are you at liberty to specify the names of projects you work on and if applicable the associated grants that fund them?

Project name	Associated Grant
I do not wish to enclose	

Q11 Is there a specific part of the project budget reserved for maintaining the research software during the project?

- Yes.
- No, but there is another budget for software maintenance. Please specify the budget source:
- No, there is no budget specified for software maintenance during the project. (3)
- The research software I work with/ or develop doesn't require to be maintained after the project ends.
- Other

Q12 In case there is a need to maintain the research software, is there a budget available, either through the grant that funds the project or through other means, to maintain the research software after the project ends?

- Yes, there are funds for maintenance reserved from the project budget for after the project.
- Yes, there are other funds available for software maintenance after the project ends.
- No, but it is expected that the community that uses the software will maintain the software after the project.
- There is no budget available for maintaining the software after the project.
- No, but it is expected that new grants will be obtained to finance maintenance.

Q13 Is there a dedicated budget in your organization for maintaining the research software?

- Yes
- No, but there is another budget for software maintenance (Please specify the budget source).
- No, there is no budget specified for software maintenance.

Q14 Do you know why there is no dedicated budget for maintaining the research software?

- I do not know and have no idea why there is no dedicated budget for maintaining the research software.
- I do not know for sure, but I think I know the reason (Please explain).

- I do know why there is no dedicated budget for maintaining research software (Please explain).

Q15 How is the funding available for maintaining the software code used? (More than one option can be selected)

- To hire dedicated personnel.
- To have existing personnel write hours on the project.

To invest in infrastructure.

Other (Please specify):

Q16 How much of the project budget is reserved for software maintenance?

Please fill in a percentage of your project budget that is reserved for software maintenance.

I do not know.

Q17 Are the people responsible for maintaining the research software you work on (including yourself) explicitly tasked with this responsibility in their job description or annual work plan?

Yes.

No.

I don't know.

Q18 What is the career stage or job title of the individuals responsible for maintaining the research software you work with (including yourself)?

PhD student (Dutch: promovendi).

Postdoctoral fellow.

Assistant professor on a temporary contract (i.e., "tenure tracker").

Assistant, an associate or a full professor on a permanent contract (i.e., "tenured").

Researcher (In a university: not part of the academic career track).

Lecturer

Research software engineer/ developer/ programmer

Other (Please specify): _____

Q19 How much of the contract time of the individuals responsible for maintaining the research software you work with (including yourself) is allocated for software maintenance?

Please fill in a percentage of the contract-time that is reserved for software maintenance.

I do not know.

Q20 How much of the actual working time of the individuals responsible for maintaining the research software you work with (including yourself) is dedicated to software maintenance?

Please fill in an estimated percentage of the actual work time that is used for software maintenance.

I do not know.

Q21 What do you consider to be the biggest challenges concerning the maintenance and dissemination of research software? How do you rate the importance of these challenges on a scale from 1 to 5 (1: not important at all, 5: extremely important)?

Challenge	Importance

Q22 Is consideration given to work on research software in the career decisions of those involved in its development (including yourself)?

- Both the work on developing the research software and maintaining the research software are valued in the career decision.
- The work on developing the research software is valued in the career decision but the work on maintaining the research software is not.
- The work on developing the research software is not valued in the career decision, but the work on maintaining the research software is.
- Neither the work on developing the research software nor on maintaining the research software is valued in the career decision.
- Other (Please specify):

Q23 Do the people working on the maintenance of the research software you work with (including yourself) write hours in a financial administrative system?

- Yes.
- No.
- I do not know.

Q24 How do the people working on the maintenance of the research software you work with (including yourself) write the hours they work on maintenance of the software?

- They write it under the project, labeled “research (or similar)”.
- They write it under the project, labeled “engineering (or similar)”.
- They write it under the project, labeled something else (please specify):
- They write it under a post that is not the project (please specify) labeled “research (or similar)”:
- They write it under a post that is not the project (please specify) labeled “engineering (or similar)”.
- They write it under a post that is not the project (please specify) labeled something else (please specify).

I do not know.

Q25 Does your organization measure the value or impact of research software developed in the organization in any way that you know of? (More than one option can be selected).

It is measured using citations to papers related to the software.

It is measured using the number of downloads of the software.

It is measured using the number of users of the software.

It is measured through how much it is adopted by others, including, but not limited to commercial use, use by governments and/or other academics.

It is measured in another way (please explain).

It is not measured.

I do not know.

Q26 Do you have any comments about the issues covered in this survey or the survey itself?

Appendix 3 – Branching logic

Here is a structured breakdown of key branching points and conditional logic in the survey:

1. Early Exit Conditions

Consent Question

If the participant does not agree to participate, they are skipped to the end of the survey.

Q4: "Which of the following activities concerning research software do you spend your work time on?"

If the participant selects "None", they are skipped to the end of the survey.

2. Conditional Question Paths

Q9: "Is the research software you work with developed in a specific project? If so, do you know how this project is funded?"

If the participant selects:

"Not part of a project", they are directed to Q9.1: "Do you know how your work with research software is funded?"

Any other funded project option, they proceed to the next general funding-related question.

Q10: "Are you at liberty to specify the names of projects you work on and if applicable the associated grants that fund them?"

This question is only shown if Q9 = a funded project (options 4, 5, 6, or 7).

Q11: "Is there a specific part of the project budget reserved for maintaining the research software during the project?"

This question is only shown if Q9 = a funded project (options 4, 5, 6, or 7).

Q12: "Is there a budget available to maintain the research software after the project ends?"

This question is only shown if Q9 = a funded project (options 4, 5, 6, or 7).

Q13: "Is there a dedicated budget in your organization for maintaining the research software?"

This question is only asked if Q9 = a funded project (options 4, 5, 6, or 7).

Q14: "Do you know why there is no dedicated budget for maintaining research software?"

This question is only shown if Q13 = "No, there is no budget specified for software maintenance."

Q15: "How is the funding available for maintaining the software code used?"

This question is only asked if Q11 = Yes OR Q12 = Yes.

Q23: "Do the people working on the maintenance of the research software write hours in a financial administrative system?"

If the answer is "Yes", then Q24: "How do they write the hours?" is displayed.

3. Impact & Measurement Questions

Q25: "Does your organization measure the value or impact of research software?"

This question provides multiple answers (citations, downloads, usage, external adoption, etc.).

If they select "It is measured in another way", they are asked to specify.

Q26: "Do you have any comments about the issues covered in this survey?"

This is the final *open-ended* feedback question.

References

¹Gruenpeter, M. (2021) "Defining Research Software: a controversial discussion". Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5504016.

²Martinez-Ortiz, C. (2023) "Practical guide to Software Management Plans". Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7589725.